

POTENTIOMETRIC STUDIES OF OXIDES OF MANGANESE

BY S. K. K. JATKAR AND V. B. MAINKAR

Manganous sulphate has been titrated with potassium permanganate and *vice versa*, using the electrode system Pt/sol K_2SO_4 sat. $N-H_2SO_4/Hg_2SO_4/Hg$. The nature of the curve of E. M. F. and $\Delta E/\Delta$ c.c. - c.c. confirms the formation of the known oxides of manganese. These curves would further indicate that in solution there are more complex changes taking place in the structure of manganese ion with progressive oxidation. These changes are being studied further.

There are six well defined oxides of manganese : (1) MnO , (2) Mn_3O_4 , (3) Mn_2O_7 , (4) MnO_2 , (5) MnO_3 and (6) Mn_2O_3 . Besides these a number of intermediate oxides have been reported in literature (cf. Mellor, "A Comprehensive Treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry", Vol. XII, pp. 220-237).

MnO .—Manganese monoxide or manganous oxide has been obtained by heating manganous salts like $MnCO_3$, $Mn(OH)_2$, MnC_2O_4 or by reducing the higher oxides in a stream of H_2 or CO . The crystals of this oxide are emerald-green.

Mn_3O_4 .—Manganosic oxide or trimanganese tetroxide is regarded by some as a compound corresponding to $2MnO \cdot MnO_2$ because of its behaviour in nitric acid.

Mn_2O_3 .—Manganic oxide or manganese hemitrioxide occurs as the mineral Braunite. It is prepared by heating MnO_2 or $Mn(NO_3)_2$.

The hydrated Mn_2O_3 , *i. e.* $Mn_2O_3 \cdot H_2O$, has also been prepared by passing air through a solution of a manganous salt in ammoniacal NH_4Cl . It is also prepared by reduction of $KMnO_4$ by sodium arsenite solution at $60^\circ-70^\circ$.

Because the dilute acids decompose it into MnO and MnO_2 , it has been regarded as $MnO \cdot MnO_2$. Laspeyres (cf. Mellor, *loc. cit.*) supposed it to be a manganese salt of H_6MnO_6 , *i. e.* Mn_3MnO_6 , while Groth ("Chemische Krystallographie", 1906, I, p. 115) gives it a formula $MnMnO_3$. The hydrated oxide was regarded by Franke (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1889, 27, 36, 31, 166, 451) and Zanko and Stefanovskii (*J. Gen. Chem. USSR.*, 1934, 4, 404) as being constituted with bi- and quadrivalent manganese.

MnO_2 .—Manganese dioxide containing less than the theoretical amount of oxygen is formed by the oxidation of solutions of manganous salts. This is achieved either chemically by oxidising agents, such as bleaching powder, persulphates, permanganates, etc., or by electrolytic oxidation. Hydrated MnO_2 was prepared by passing SO_2 in

a solution of KMnO_4 at 75° with a composition $\text{MnO}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$. It is also obtained when a manganous salt is treated with an oxidising agent.

According to Geloso (*Bull. soc. chim.*, 1925, 37, 641) in the titration of a solution of KMnO_4 with 0.1N-sodium arsenite within a certain range of concentration of H_2SO_4 , the manganese oxide is reduced to Mn_3O_4 ; in neutral solution or with insufficient acid, a brown turbidity or a yellow coloration is obtained, whilst an excess of acid gives a pink solution, the corresponding states of oxidation of manganese ranging continuously from MnO_2 through Mn_6O_{11} , and Mn_3O_4 to Mn_2O_3 . But he adds that the variation in composition of the reduction product with various conditions proves that the formulae Mn_3O_4 and Mn_6O_{11} do not represent definite compounds, the green solutions being a colloidal solution of MnO_2 with other substances adsorbed.

A group of oxides between MnO_2 and MnO has been reported. These are manganous manganites or permanganites of the type $\text{MnO} \cdot n\text{MnO}_2$. Guyard (*Chem. News*, 1863, 8, 292; *Bull. soc. chim.*, 1864, ii, 1, 89) obtained $3\text{MnO} \cdot 2\text{MnO}_2$ and $\text{MnO} \cdot 5\text{MnO}_2$ (Mn_6O_{11}) by the action of manganous salts on KMnO_4 or K_2MnO_4 . Pickering (cf. Mellor, *loc. cit.*) obtained products ranging between $5\text{MnO} \cdot 16\text{MnO}_2$ ($\text{Mn}_{21}\text{O}_{37}$) and $5\text{MnO} \cdot 36\text{MnO}_2$ ($\text{Mn}_{41}\text{O}_{77}$). Franke (*loc. cit.*) reported $2\text{MnO} \cdot 3\text{MnO}_2$ (Mn_5O_8); Reissig (cf. Mellor, *loc. cit.*), $\text{MnO} \cdot 2\text{MnO}_2$ (Mn_3O_4); Carnot (cf. Mellor, *loc. cit.*), $\text{MnO} \cdot 5\text{MnO}_2$ (Mn_6O_{11}). The compound $\text{MnO} \cdot 5\text{MnO}_2$ has been obtained by many others as well. Spring and Lucion (cf. Mellor, *loc. cit.*) and Carnot (*loc. cit.*) obtained $\text{MnO} \cdot 10\text{MnO}_2$ ($\text{Mn}_{11}\text{O}_{21}$) by treating a manganous salt with nitric acid.

The reaction between permanganate and manganous salts is of very great interest. Guyard (*loc. cit.*) suggested the reaction to be

By adding known equivalents of a manganous salt with one equivalent of permanganate he obtained the following compounds: $5\text{MnO} \cdot \text{Mn}_2\text{O}_7$ (Mn_7O_{12}), $4\text{MnO} \cdot \text{Mn}_2\text{O}_7$ (Mn_6O_{11}) and $3\text{MnO} \cdot \text{Mn}_2\text{O}_7$ (Mn_5O_{10}); the first and second are formed in the cold but the third in hot solution; Mn_7O_{12} or $5\text{MnO} \cdot \text{Mn}_2\text{O}_7$ of a violet-brown colour gives Mn_3O_4 when calcined at high temperatures out of contact with air. Guyard calls these compounds manganese permanganates.

Geloso and Dubios (cf. Mellor, *loc. cit.*) considered that the reduction of permanganates by manganous salts did not form a definite compound but there was rather a continuous variation in the degree of oxidation of the pseudo-dioxides formed. According to Baubigny (cf. Mellor, *loc. cit.*) the precipitation of manganese dioxide from an acid solution of a manganous salt by potassium permanganate depends on the acidity, on the concentration of the salt and on the temperature. The acid retards precipitation. The precipitate contains less oxygen than is required for MnO_2 owing to adsorption of some manganous salts and to the co-precipitation of some manganic acid.

The purpose of the present investigation was to find out if the oxides intermediate between MnO and Mn_2O_7 could be shown by potentiometrically titrating manganous sulphate and potassium permanganate. The scheme of reactions for the formation of the well known oxides of manganese in the titration may be represented as follows:

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The electrode system used in this work was

The potentials were measured on a Tinsley vernier potentiometer using a sensitive mirror galvanometer as null instrument. The manganous sulphate was titrated with permanganate and *vice versa* using solutions of varying acidity.

Figures 1 to 4 show the plots of E. M. F. and $\Delta E / \Delta \text{c.c.}$ against c.c. The summary is given in Tables I and II. Table I shows the comparison of the observed volume of the reagent added to obtain the required peak with that calculated on the basis that the precipitated compound has the formula shown.

TABLE I

MnO/Mn ₂ O ₇ (calc.)	10 c.c. M/10 KMnO ₄ + M/10-MnSO ₄ (calc.)	10 c.c. M/10 aq. KMnO ₄ + M/10-MnSO ₄ (observed).	10 c.c. M/10 acid KMnO ₄ + M/10-MnSO ₄ (observed).	10 c.c. M/10 Alk. KMnO ₄ + M/10-MnSO ₄ (observed).	50 c.c. M/10 MnSO ₄ + M/10-KMnO ₄ (calc.)	50 c.c. aq M/10-MnSO ₄ + M/10 KMnO ₄ (observed).
0.08	0.36 c.c.	—	—	0.35 c.c.	—	—
0.10	0.43	—	0.45 c.c.	—	—	—
0.12	0.54	—	—	—	—	—
0.16	0.70	—	—	—	—	—
0.25	1.10	1.35 c.c.	1.05	0.95	—	—
0.50 Mn ₂ O ₃	2.15	2.05	2.10	2.25	—	—
1	4.30	4.15	4.30	4.75	—	—
1.5	6.45	—	—	7.25	61.00 c.c.	60.00 c.c.
2	8.60	8.50	—	8.45	45.90	46.50
3 Mn ₂ O ₃	12.90	12.85	12.75	12.95	30.50	30.50
3.5	15.05	14.90	14.45	15.25	26.10	26.30
4	17.20	17.50	16.90	—	21.00	22.90
5	21.50	—	21.50	—	18.40	17.70
6	—	—	—	—	15.30	15.10
7	—	—	—	—	13.10	13.15
8 Mn ₂ O ₃	—	—	—	—	11.50	11.65
10	—	—	—	—	10.10	10.55
12	—	—	—	—	7.70	7.75
13 Mn ₂ O ₄	—	—	—	—	—	—
24	—	—	—	—	3.80	3.20
36	—	—	—	—	2.50	2.30
48	—	—	—	—	1.90	1.95
84	—	—	—	—	1.10	1.05

FIG. 3
 Titration of alk. KMnO_4 with MnSO_4 .
 Oxides of manganese () ratio $\text{MnO}/\text{Mn}_2\text{O}_7$

FIG. 4
 Titration of MnSO_4 with KMnO_4 .
 Oxides of manganese () ratio $\text{MnO}/\text{Mn}_2\text{O}_7$.

Table II shows the comparison of the calculated ratio of $MnO : Mn_2O_7$, with that observed, along with the values of the peak $\Delta E / \Delta c.c.$ in parentheses

TABLE II

Formula.	Decimal formula MnO_x .	Ratio MnO/Mn_2O_7 (calc.)	Ratio of MnO/Mn_2O_7 (observed).			
			Aq. $KMnO_4$ + $MnSO_4$.	Acid- $KMnO_4$ + $MnSO_4$.	Alk. $KMnO_4$ + $MnSO_4$.	Aq. $MnSO_4$ + Aq. $KMnO_4$.
Mn_2O_7	$MnO_{3.5}$	—	—	—	—	—
—	—	0.08	—	—	0.08 (-30)	—
—	—	0.10	—	0.11 (20)	—	—
—	—	0.12	—	—	—	—
—	—	0.16	—	—	—	—
—	—	0.25	0.30 (60)	0.25 (-10)	0.22 (-30)	—
$Mn_{2.5}O_{7.5}$ (MnO_3)	$MnO_{3.0}$	0.50	0.48 (40)	0.49 (-5)	0.52 (-10)	—
Mn_3O_8	$MnO_{2.66}$	1	0.97 (20)	1.01 (-25)	1.10 (35)	—
$Mn_{3.66}O_{8.5}$	$MnO_{2.43}$	1.50	—	—	1.68 (570)	1.52 (0.5)
Mn_4O_9	$MnO_{2.25}$	2	1.99 (15)	—	1.96 (190)	1.97 (1)
Mn_5O_{10} (MnO_2)	$MnO_{2.00}$	3	3.00 (-40)	3.00 (-7)	3.00 (80)	3.00 (75)
$Mn_{5.5}O_{10.5}$	$MnO_{1.81}$	3.50	3.48 (-80)	3.40 (-90)	3.53 (-160)	3.48 (10)
Mn_6O_{11}	$MnO_{1.83}$	4	4.08 (-35)	3.98 (-25)	—	4.00 (10)
Mn_7O_{12}	$MnO_{1.71}$	5	—	5.06 (-7.5)	—	5.17 (10)
Mn_8O_{13}	$MnO_{1.62}$	6	—	—	—	6.06 (20)
Mn_9O_{14}	$MnO_{1.55}$	7	—	—	—	6.96 (20)
$Mn_{10}O_{15}$ (Mn_2O_3)	$MnO_{1.50}$	8	—	—	—	7.85 (-40)
$Mn_{12}O_{17}$	$MnO_{1.42}$	10	—	—	—	8.67 (-30)
$Mn_{14}O_{19}$	$MnO_{1.28}$	12	—	—	—	11.80 (30)
$Mn_{15}O_{20}$ (Mn_3O_4)	$MnO_{1.33}$	13	—	—	—	—
—	—	24	—	—	—	28.60 (40)
—	—	36	—	—	—	39.80 (80)
—	—	48	—	—	—	46.00 (-80)
—	—	84	—	—	—	87.10 (160)
MnO	MnO	—	—	—	—	—

DISCUSSION

The hypothesis of Guyard, that by reacting manganous sulphate and permanganate compounds with definite ratios of MnO and Mn_2O_7 , are formed, has been substantiated by the present work.

The sharp initial changes in the $\Delta E/\Delta c.c.$ during the potentiometric titration of permanganate with manganous sulphate are due to the formation of MnO_3 , which requires the peaks to occur at 2.15, 1.10, 0.70, 0.54, 0.45, 0.35 c.c. etc. most of which are shown prominently in the graphs, the peak corresponding to the complete precipitation of MnO_3 being obtained at 2.15. With further addition of manganous sulphate, the peaks are obtained for a compound having a ratio 1. But with the addition of more manganous sulphate to the alkaline permanganate, a strong indication (peak value 570)

of a complex of the ratio 1.5 is obtained. This oxide, which is not reported in literature, is also shown very feebly (peak value 0.5) in the reverse titration.

With further additions of manganous sulphate to aqueous and alkaline permanganate, peaks are obtained at ratio 2, which are also present in the reverse titration. The next peak occurs at ratio 3 in all the titrations corresponding to the precipitation of manganese dioxide.

The strongest peak occurs at ratio 3.5 which corresponds to the oxide $Mn_{11}O_{21}$, reported by Celoso (*loc. cit.*) and Guyard (*loc. cit.*). The point is not so prominent in the reverse titration. The peaks for the compound corresponding to ratio 4 are obtained in both the forward and backward titrations except in the case of alkaline permanganate. The corresponding oxide has been reported by Guyard. The oxide of ratio 5, reported by Guyard, is shown only in the acidic and reverse titration.

The titration of manganous sulphate with permanganate shows marked periodicity with peaks at intervals of molecular ratios 84, 48, 36, 24 and 12 indicating the formation of the compound of ratio 12, the nearest known oxide being Mn_3O_4 (ratio 13.) This complex is oxidised in steps of two *i. e.*, $12 \rightarrow 10 \rightarrow 8$, the last being the known oxide Mn_2O_3 . Further oxidation strangely enough goes in steps of $8 \rightarrow 7 \rightarrow 6$ etc., corresponding oxides are not reported in literature.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY OF POONA,
POONA 4

Received October 6, 1950.